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Short Report

The beneficial impact of glucose supplementation in a patient with PDH Cytopathy

Abstract

This case report explores the diagnosis and effective management of a mid-aged male patient initially suspected of having Metabolic Syndrome. The use of continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) technology led to a surprisingly bold identification of stress-induced gluconeogenesis associated with PDH (Pyruvate Dehydrogenase) cytopathy, necessitating a revision of the initial diagnosis.

Introduction

A 46-year-old male patient from Italy who was initially suspected of suffering from metabolic syndrome for 25 years ask for our help since his condition was progressive and definitely much more serious than 'just' a Metabolic Syndrome. Under our observation, it was soon discovered that he was indeed not suffering from metabolic syndrome at all, but from Oshtoran syndrome (H63D Syndrome Type 3). Part of this very rare disease, especially in advanced cases, is a PDH cytopathy (pyruvate dehydrogenase). The introduction of glucose live sensors revealed, after the blood tests were done, an underlying PDH (Pyruvate Dehydrogenase) cytopathy, leading to a revision of the diagnosis and the discovery of effective management strategies involving glucose supplementation.^{4,5,6,8}

Patient background

The suffering patient presented with an astonishing collection of 62 symptoms, more

than 30% consistent with Metabolic Syndrome. The rest was a wild systemic mix with a focus on neurological symptoms like fatigue, brain fog, cognitive impairment, reduction of his IQ, and most severe narcolepsy-like episodes, especially postprandial. Initial assessments included standard blood glucose monitoring, which failed to capture the critical metabolic fluctuations underlying his condition, even with the best and most advanced glucose measure devices.

Discovery with 24/7 glucose live sensors

The introduction of live continuous glucose monitoring (CGM/live) using sensors which provide real-time data on the patient's blood glucose levels revealed unexpected patterns and a severe misdiagnosis. Thanks to the existence of a new device for live observation of the patients blood sugar and testing his lactate value every 2 hours we found most astonishing patterns.

1. Plateaus of blood glucose levels between 120 and 155 mg/dl for extended periods.
2. Sudden spikes in glucose levels to 115-130 mg/dl during stress or fasting periods (= no meal, snack, or sugared drink for at least 3 hours.)

These results indicated clearly stress-induced gluconeogenesis and definitely not typical mechanisms and patterns of metabolic syndrome.

Pathophysiology

PDH cytopathy impairs the conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA, limiting ATP production via the citric acid cycle. This metabolic block forces the body to rely on anaerobic glycolysis, resulting in:

- *Increased lactate production.
- *Metabolic acidosis and/or inefficient ATP production.
- *Stress-induced gluconeogenesis leading to erratic blood glucose spikes.
- *Erratic levels of triglycerides
- *Unusually rapid changes in total cholesterol, HDL and LDL

Intervention and management

To address these metabolic challenges, the patient was administered small doses of glucose (dextrose) at the first signs of stress-induced gluconeogenesis and postprandially over a period 30 to 120 minutes. This intervention was guided by the real-time data from the glucose live sensors.

Results

Complete normalization of blood glucose levels was observed after the first few treatments: The immediate availability of exogenous glucose reduced the need for gluconeogenesis to stabilize blood glucose levels. What's more, the administration of glucose effectively prevented narcolepsy-like episodes, muscle weakness, and cognitive impairment by providing a quick energy source. Reduced gluconeogenesis, decreased the metabolic burden on the liver, alleviating the fluctuating hepatic steatosis observed in the patient.^{19,20}

Discussion

The use of CGM technology was crucial in changing the diagnosis from metabolic syndrome to PDH cytopathy. Real-time monitoring enabled accurate and timely glucose supplementation with the following effects:

- * Alleviation of the consequences of catecholamine-driven gluconeogenesis and associated symptoms as well as the postprandial gluconeogenesis.
- * Narcolepsy became 80% less frequent and 65% less aggressive.
- * Provides an immediate source of energy, compensates for the inefficiency of ATP production due to the PDH defect.
- * Reduces the metabolic burden on the liver due to unnecessary gluconeogenesis.

Conclusion

This case study highlights the critical role of continuous glucose monitoring in the diagnosis and treatment of rare metabolic disorders such as PDH cytopathy. Timely administration of glucose based on real-time sensor data is a practical and effective strategy to alleviate the symptoms and metabolic disturbances associated with this disease.

Conflicts of interest
none

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